

Benchmarking OpenIFS with ESDM and XIOS

Deliverable D4.3-B

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1 Abstract

The ability to conduct and analyze exascale simulations requires efficient input/output (I/O) operations. When dealing with enormous volumes of data, any inefficient I/O operation will hinder the overall productivity and the provided resources will not be used to their full capacity. Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) is designed to improve I/O operations during simulation runs together with XML Input/Output server (XIOS), which is the default I/O scheme in the Open Integrated Forecasting System (OpenIFS), a derivative of IFS from European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). Benchmark tests performed on Tco1279L139 cubic octahedral grid show that by increasing the number of XIOS servers, a significant reduction in I/O operation time can be observed. Moreover, enabling ESDM reduces I/O time even further.

2 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	X
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	X

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	X
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	X
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	X
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	X
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	X

3 Introduction

One of the main objectives of ESiWACE is to push the limits of climate and weather models to perform simulations at extremely high-resolutions. In other words, enabling exascale climate computing. Achieving this goal involves development of many aspects of the project such as performance tuning, porting of the code to new hardware with the aid of domain specific languages (DSLs), provisioning of visualization tools to support the analysis of high-resolution model output data as well as optimizing the model's I/O. Each of these components plays a significant role in making a model ready for exascale computation. Optimizations for I/O is addressed by Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) Kunkel and Pedro (2020), which handles the complexities in the storage tiers. It exploits the structural information exposed by workflows, applications as

well as the data description formats of HDF5 or NetCDF to organize data and metadata more efficiently across a variety of storage back-ends. The ESDM data model is, similar to NetCDF, a self-describing on-disk data format for storing structured data. From an application's perspective, ESDM acts as a drop-in replacement for typical use-cases as no additional configuration to the code is required.

This report investigates the performance of the I/O library XIOS for climate models while utilizing ESDM as its middleware by executing benchmarks on the OpenIFS model. The benchmarks were run on Emmy (the HPC systems of the GWDG) using hardware configurations similar to real world use-cases and were set out to determine the optimal software configurations for XIOS and ESDM that provide the greatest performance improvements.

OpenIFS¹ is a climate and weather model provided by ECMWF. While OpenIFS facilitates research and teaching in numerical weather prediction up to seasonal timescales, it is also made accessible for use in academic and research institutions. Even though, the OpenIFS model has the same forecast potential as the IFS (Integrated Forecasting System), it does not have the data assimilation aspect but it is an easy-to-use model because of the provided software and relevant documentation.

For the experiments, various OpenIFS grid resolutions were used. These resolutions are noted in the form TxxxxLyyyy, where the xxxx is the code representing the grid resolution and yyyy represents the vertical levels. For instance, in T1279L137 the 1279 represents the grid resolution which is 9km approx. and 137 is number of vertical levels.

XIOS² is a library dedicated to I/O management, designed to manage NetCDF outputs of climate models. Its main features include the management of output diagnostics and history files, temporal post-processing operations, (e.g., average, min, max) and spatial post-processing operations (e.g., arithmetic operations, re-gridding). XIOS simplifies I/O management by reducing the number of I/O operations and arguments in the source code. The output definitions are outsourced into XML files, which can be changed without re-compilation of the source code. XIOS achieves high-performance by utilizing asynchronous and parallel I/O operations through MPI.

ESDM³ or Earth System Data Middleware can handle I/O efficiently and supports data storage for multiple backends. The flexible I/O semantics provided by ESDM simplify the mapping of datasets to multiple storage locations. ESDM is able to insert itself as an alternative middleware for an parallel application (and including XIOS) to provide improved performance by 1) changing the on-disk format of NetCDF, 2) by using runtime parameters and background threads to read/write data in large I/Os, and 3) by storing data on multiple storage systems at the same time.

ESDM was introduced in Kunkel and Pedro (2020) and further developed in deliverable D4.1 Betke et al. (2021).

4 Preliminary benchmark results

4.1 Hardware Setup

The T1279L137 model run was performed on the Emmy supercomputer on standard:96 partitions. Each node in this partition has a dual socket Intel Xeon Platinum 9242 (192 cores total) with 380 GB memory. The model runs were performed with various combinations of cores and threads, which resulted in partial or full node resource utilization. This was done to determine the optimal configuration of resources per node.

¹https://www.esiwace.eu/services/software-support/sup_OpenIFS

²<http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/wiki>

³<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>

A minimum of 4 nodes were required to start a model run successfully. A model run was limited to calculate 6 hours of data with hourly output. The scaling of the model was done first to figure out the optimal combinations of cores and threads and then fixing these values before varying the number of XIOS servers to measure the performance of I/O. Furthermore, to set a baseline, some of the runs were done with I/O turned off so they can be compared to runs with I/O enabled. For the sake of consistency, the majority of the model runs were performed on 10 nodes, with various configurations run up to 40 nodes.

After a few initial experiments, it was already visible that the model scales well with a higher number of cores per node with fewer threads. For instance, 45 processes with 2 threads per node and 30 processes with 6 threads per node took the least amount of time compared to cases where a higher number of threads than processes were configured. In practice, the combination of processes and threads most commonly used in the community is 8 processes and 6 threads per process.

4.2 Software Stack

The software stack is built with the following software on Emmy, which has CentOS Linux 7 operating system:

- GCC 9.3.0
- OpenMPI 3.1.5
- HDF5 1.12.1
- ESDM NetCDF
- NetCDF-Fortran 4.5.3
- XIOS 2.5
- Eccodes 2.24.2
- OIFS 43r3v1

No extra optimizations were applied while compiling OpenIFS and XIOS. Earlier studies have shown that compiling XIOS with `-O3` optimization flag will yield notable improvements in terms of model execution time Yepes-Arbós et al. (2022). So, applying the `-O3` optimization will certainly improve the performance results shown in the benchmarks but the overall performance profile will still remain the same.

4.3 Experiment Outline

As there are many aspects that influence I/O performance and its evaluation, the core idea of these benchmarks was to perform experiments where OpenIFS CY43R3 in combination with XIOS and ESDM is used as well as to test a case where only XIOS and ESDM are used without OpenIFS. In the latter case, OpenIFS is replaced with an **XIOS test client** that produces dummy data. The performance profiles of XIOS and ESDM from the test client case serve as a reference to better understand the performance profile generated using OpenIFS.

Preliminary runs were conducted with the following resolutions: T255L91 (c.a. 39 km), T511L91 (c.a. 23 km) and T1279L137 (c.a. 9 km) cubic octahedral grid with vertical levels 91, 91, 137 respectively. The T1279L137 grid was preferred over the other option as it produces a reasonable amount of data at each time-step, amounting to an overall size of 507 GB (6 time-steps). Scalability and performance measurement of I/O operations on larger data-sets are more prominently visible than on data-sets whose data volume is relatively small in size.

The model was simulated for 6 hours and the output frequency was set to every hour. Running the model for a shorter duration than 6 hours would have the same I/O operational pattern no matter how many time steps are written out to disk.

Figure 1: The model run time in seconds is shown in the figure with I/O turned off on a 10 node configuration. Strong scaling can be seen with more processors than threads per node, which is to be expected. The darker the shade of blue the better the results. The gray area indicates lack of data.

To get baseline measurement of the model, a few experiments were done with I/O turned off. The advantage of doing these experiments is two fold; (1) To find an optimal configuration of processes and OpenMP threads per process so as to fix these parameters in the rest of the model runs and (2) these act as a reference for comparing model runs done with I/O enabled.

Fig. 1 presents a heat map showing the number of processes-per-node against the number of OpenMP threads-per-process. As shown in the plot, more processes with fewer threads-per-process perform better than the other way around. For model runs without I/O, it is reasonable to go for as many processes-per-node as possible but when I/O is enabled, keeping the distribution of XIOS servers in view, it might not be feasible to optimize by maximizing processes-per-node. Therefore, 15 processes-per-node and 6 threads-per-process was chosen for the majority of the I/O enabled model runs.

4.4 Benchmark Results

In this section, the benchmark results for the following cases are discussed:

- OpenIFS Model runs without I/O enabled
- OpenIFS Model run with I/O enabled
- (XIOS) test client runs with I/O enabled

Invocation of the model run commonly is done as follows

```
$OIFS_HOME/bin/oifs_run \  
-g o \  
--xios \  
--xios-nproc 20 \  
--res 1279 \  
--nproc 330 \  
--threads 6 \  

```

```
--oifs-exe \  
./master.exe b0r7
```

The `oifs_run` wrapper script updates the parameters in the necessary locations and sources environmental variables prior to invoking `mpirun` call. Alternatively, the `mpirun` call can also be invoked directly as follows, provided the rest of the parameters are manually updated in the necessary locations prior to invoking the call:

```
mpirun -np 330 ./master.exe : -np 20 ./xios_server.exe
```

These two types of invocations would put XIOS servers on dedicated node(s). If distributing the XIOS servers across all available compute nodes is desired, then the `mpirun` is invoked as follows:

```
mpirun -np 80 --map-by node ./master.exe : -np 8 ./xios_server.exe
```

The `map-by node` option distributes the processes equally on all nodes such that XIOS servers on the local nodes are available.

In table 1, experiment runs with dedicated nodes for XIOS servers and distributed XIOS servers across compute nodes (`map-by node`) are shown. In all of these runs, 15 processes per node and 6 threads per process were used. The model was run with T1279L137 grid resolution for 6 hours with hourly output frequency. As shown in the table, distributing XIOS server across compute nodes performs better than using dedicated XIOS server nodes.

Compute nodes	XIOS dedicated nodes	XIOS servers per node	total XIOS servers	Execution time (seconds)	type
10	0	1	10	1440	distributed
10	0	5	50	1200	distributed
10	0	15	150	1260	distributed
10	3	15	45	1910	dedicated
10	4	15	60	2026	dedicated
10	10	5	50	error	dedicated

Table 1: XIOS servers: dedicated versus distributed nodes

Table 2 presents the results of a number of experiments done on a larger number of nodes with the focus on investigating ESDM performance. All the runs with ESDM enabled generate data volumes of 1014 GB and 507 GB when it is disabled. The reason for doubling the size of the data volumes is due to ESDM using double precision to store the data while XIOS alone uses single precision. The throughput presented in the table is calculated for the data volume that was produced.

As 6 OpenMP threads were used for all the runs, the number of processes multiplied with threads gives the total number of cores used for computation. Apart from the first two runs (i.e., 40+3 node configuration), in the rest of the runs XIOS servers are distributed across all the compute nodes.

ESDM seems to perform well with fewer XIOS server on both 40 and 80 node configuration. Increasing the number of XIOS servers gradually degrades ESDM performance where as runs without ESDM enabled improves the throughput performance before flattening out with too many XIOS servers. We want to highlight that with a throughput of 12.8 GB/s on 40 compute nodes neither of the XIOS benchmarks is utilizing the available storage bandwidth on Emmy which yields 85 GiB/s on 16 nodes (with IO500).

Compute nodes	total processes	total XIOS servers	XIOS servers per node	Execution time (seconds)	ESDM	throughput GB/s
40+3	800	60	20	428	off	3.4
40+3	800	60	20	422	on	6.4
40	760	40	1	443	off	3.1
40	760	40	1	358	on	12.8
80	1520	80	1	207	off	7.18
80	1520	80	1	288	on	6.66
80	1520	160	2	224	off	5.77
80	1520	160	2	271	on	7.54
80	1520	240	3	223	off	5.8
80	1520	240	3	547	on	2.4

Table 2: XIOS servers: Throughput with and without ESDM (best configurations are in bold font)

4.4.1 Baseline case

The focus of the control runs is to provide a baseline measurement of the computation time without any I/O operations. These measurements serve as a reference to compare to model runs with I/O output.

Multiple control runs were performed with varying numbers of threads and processes to determine the scaling of the model with varying resources. The choice of number of processes and threads is made in such a way that either full nodes or half nodes are utilized. The number of processes and threads is scaled as multiples of 2. The number of nodes is kept the same (10 nodes) among these runs such that the measurements are comparable.

Results of these experiments are shown in Figure 1. The control runs show a strong scaling with increasing number of processes compared to the number of threads. Further scaling is achieved by allocating additional nodes.

4.5 Contribution

4.5.1 New XIOS Benchmark

The test client that is provided with XIOS works well enough to test, whether the software is properly compiled but is not good enough to measure the I/O performance as the volume of data it produces is limited to 2 MB. Therefore, we extended the test client to support higher grid resolution and a higher number of variables. After compiling the test client, the grid resolution can be changed, if desired, for each experimental run. For increasing the number of variables, there is no option implemented yet but source code modification to accommodate it are relatively straightforward.

The following code snippet is a Python script that prepares the test client run script by updating the necessary fields in relevant files. Most of the parameters this script accepts are self explanatory. The parameters `ni_glo` and `nj_glo` define the grid resolution. By default ESDM is enabled and can be disabled with the `-e` flag. The Slurm directive for specifying partitions on the compute nodes has the default value of `'standard96:test'`, which is specific to the Emmy supercomputer. In case of running this code on another machine, the partition has to be changed accordingly.

```
> ./make_runscripts.py --defaults
----- namelist -----
ni_glo ..... (-x) = 100
nj_glo ..... (-y) = 100
```

```

sleep_ms ..... (-s) = 500000
timesteps ..... (-i) = 10
----- slurm -----
duration ..... (-t) = '10:00'
nodes ..... (-N) = 1
partition ..... (-p) = 'standard96:test'
tasks_per_node (-n) = 96
----- mpirun -----
threads ..... (-T) = 1
total_procs ... (-c) = 80
xios_procs .... (-X) = 2
----- esdm -----
--disable-esdm (-e) = unsets esdm in iodef.xml
-----

```

As mentioned earlier, with the new ability of specifying grid resolutions, the volume of data written changes accordingly. With higher grid resolutions, we expect according increases in data volume. For example, setting the grid resolution to 1280x2560 with 5 variables in output and 10 time steps produces 63 GB of data in a volume, making it suitable for performing I/O related analysis. Furthermore, with the sleep function, a delay of 0.5s is introduced between the computational time-step. When the delay is minimal, most of the time observed is spent on doing I/O operations but this also means stressing out the XIOS server a little bit.

Figure 2: Scaling of I/O with respect to XIOS servers used. The resources allocated in these simulations are 80 processes, 1 thread per process, 2 nodes (1 for computation and the other dedicated for XIOS). The volume of data produced per simulation is 63 GB. Increasing the number of XIOS servers significantly reduces time taken to do the I/O.

The test client experiments are done to produce performance profiles of the XIOS servers. The test client generates random data at every computational time-step. The data it generates is 63 GB in size, which is comparable to the data volume a high-resolution model produces at every time step. The performance profile as shown in Figure 2 indicates that I/O time can be reduced by provisioning additional XIOS servers.

In the top plot of the Figure 4, the progress of the model run at each and every individual time-step is plotted. One run is done with ESDM enabled and the other run with ESDM disabled. As observed in the figure there is no performance differences between these runs.

Figure 3: Scaling of I/O in terms of throughput is show, i.e., the volume of data written per second. Although the magnitude of throughput is quite lower than the expected value, it tends to fall out with increasing XIOS servers.

Figure 4: The top and bottom plots show the progress of the model run at individual time steps. The ESDM enabled case and the multiple-files output case perform almost alike where as the single-file (i.e., one file) case takes significantly longer to write data to disk. The peaks indicate I/O operations and the flat line indicate the models computational steps. Adding resources only reduces the overall computational time.

As observed in Figure 3, the throughput is less than 1 GByte/s, which is much lower than expected. The reason for this behavior is not clear but the factors that might attribute to it are the low volume of data, low number of variables and the short sleep time value, which indicates the compute time for each time step such that the XIOS servers received the load of the next computational step before having fully completed their current load.

In Figure 4, the legend has the following values: `ESDM`, `onefile` and `multifile`. The way the files are written in each of these cases differs from each other and the intention of the plot is to visualize how this impacts the I/O throughput. In the case of `ESDM`, `ESDM` is active and `multifile` is implied internally. In the case of `onefile`, there is one file written per variable group, i.e., all surface variables are written in a file and model level variables are written in another file and so on. In the case of `multifile`, it is similar to `onefile` in the sense of writing variable groups into a single file but the number of XIOS server determines how many such files are written.

XIOS OneFile with `ESDM` is from our perspective optimal, because as a user you perceive the files as they look like a single file.

In the bottom plot of Figure 4 the peaks signify the delay in writing output to disk, which become the bottleneck for the entire simulation. XIOS supports the writing of outputs either to a single file (`onefile` or also referred as shared file) or to multiple files. Opting for multiple file output or `ESDM` will reduce the I/O time compared to single file output but then the post-processing stage needs to recombine these files into a single file if needed.

These experiments provide a baseline performance of XIOS and `ESDM` without using `OpenIFS`. From the conducted experiments, it is observed that I/O performance improves by provisioning more XIOS servers but the scaling aspect diminishes after certain number of XIOS servers (see Figure 2). `Multifile` mode or `ESDM` mode perform significantly better compared to `onefile` (single file or shared file) mode (see Figure 4). Although the throughput (see Figure 3) is less than 1 GB/s, it shows a similar trend as in I/O scaling (see Figure 2).

4.5.2 OpenIFS

`OpenIFS` CY43R3 model with grid resolution T1270L137 is used to perform the benchmark test for I/O evaluation. For these experiments, 10 nodes were used with 15 processes per node and 6 OpenMP threads per process. The only parameter that was altered is the number of XIOS servers. The XIOS servers were distributed among all the nodes equally instead of using dedicated nodes.

In Figure 5, it can be observed that the I/O time is reduced when increasing the number of XIOS servers but allocating too many XIOS servers increases the I/O time. Furthermore, the figure shows the case where `ESDM` is enabled (orange line) to compare it with the case where `ESDM` is disabled (blue line). In the latter, Multiple-file option is used by XIOS. With `ESDM` enabled, the I/O performance is slightly improved but it is not clear, whether it is a significant difference.

The total volume of data written out by XIOS is 507 GB but the `ESDM` configuration writes twice that amount (1014 GB) as it writes values in double-precision for all the variables while XIOS supports variables in single-precision. Even though, `ESDM` writes twice the amount of data, the performance is almost identical to that of XIOS. For a better performance comparison between `ESDM` and XIOS, configuring them to write the same precision level (either double or single precision) would be necessary.

As shown in the Figure 6, the blue line indicates Multiple-file output, which has much better performance compared to single-file output (orange line). The single-file output or shared file both mean the same where all time-steps belonging to a group of variables are written to the same shared file irrespective of the number of XIOS servers. Whereas, multiple-file output means multiple files are written based on the number of XIOS servers used. In this case, the number of files written is proportional the number of XIOS servers.

Figure 5: Scaling of I/O with respect to XIOS servers used is plotted. The resources allocated in these simulations are 150 processes (15 processes per node), 6 thread per process, 10 nodes. The volume of data produced per simulation is 507 GB. XIOS servers are distributed across the nodes and the output choice is multiple NetCDF files. As illustrated in the plot, increasing XIOS servers reduces the IO time but the performance is degraded as more XIOS servers are allocated. Enabling ESDM (orange line) has better performance compared doing IO with XIOS alone.

Figure 6: XIOS supports writing output as NetCDF files either as a single file or multiple files. The compute resources across these experiments are kept the same, i.e., 150 cores (15 cores/node), 6 threads/node, 10 nodes and data volume of 507 GB (T1279L137 model run with 6 h output). Choosing “multiple files” as an option for output has better performance. The downside is that an on-demand post-processing step to merge data-sets might be necessary.

4.6 Discussion

The test client experiments provides an overview of the scaling features of I/O performance. Experiments done with OpenIFS CY43R3 follow similar performance profile as the test client experiments. Looking at the I/O throughput, the distributed XIOS servers configuration yields better scaling than using dedicated XIOS server nodes.

The I/O performance is also greatly influenced with the choice of the output format. Choosing `single_file` (onefile) has substantially lower I/O performance compared to `multifile` or `ESDM` for the same number of XIOS servers. The performance of `single_file` can be significantly improved by provisioning more XIOS servers. Nevertheless, it is still less performant than using `multifile` or `ESDM` for the same number of resources.

4.7 Conclusion

Multiple benchmark experiments were conducted to understand the I/O performance of OpenIFS CY43R3 using XIOS servers and also with `ESDM` enabled. The baseline experiments with I/O disabled show that the model run time scales respective to the hardware resources used. Furthermore, these experiments act as a reference to compare the experiments with I/O enabled. T1279L137 (9 km approx.) grid resolution was used for most of the experiments as it produces a reasonable volume of data at each output frequency. A distributed XIOS server model was used during the experiment runs. Increasing the number of XIOS servers reduces the time spent on doing I/O up to a certain point. `Multiple.file` output mode outperforms `single_file` output mode. `ESDM` shows similar performance characteristics as XIOS `multiple_file` output mode but as `ESDM` writes all variables as double-precision floating point values, the volume of data is double compared to regular XIOS output volume. In spite of the double volume, the throughput of `ESDM` is relatively better than `multifile` output mode. Additional experiments are necessary after fixing the double precision issue in `ESDM`.

5 References

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